

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF LARGE-SCALE WELDING OF CARBON FIBER THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

A. Beukers, D. Stavrov, H. E. N. Bersee

*Production Technology Group, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of
Technology, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS, Delft, The Netherlands*

ABSTRACT: This paper describes an experimental investigation of resistance welding of carbon fiber thermoplastics performed on large-scale welds. Carbon fiber reinforced polyetherimide (CF/PEI) was the material used for manufacturing the welding specimens, while the heating elements were produced from metallic mesh. The experiments were performed under constant pressure. Special experimental apparatus was developed that enabled uniform pressure distribution along the weld. The focus of the investigation was on studying possible solutions for current leaking in large welds. Several options for electrical insulation of the heating element were proposed and investigated. The quality of the bond was evaluated by using microscopic scanning and mechanical testing. Microscopic scanning gave information about the degree of bonding between the heating element and matrix and existence of voids. For lap shear strength testing, welded laminates were cut in coupon size and subsequently tested according to ASTM D 1002 standard. To provide a better indication of the joint quality, benchmark specimens were also manufactured and tested. The investigation revealed that a single ply of glass fiber/PEI provides satisfactory insulation, while high temperature heating element coatings are very promising.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic composite, Resistance welding, CF/PEI, Current leaking, Electrical insulation, Metallic mesh heating element.

INTRODUCTION

As the complexity of the thermoplastic structures grows over the years, joining remains a critical step in their production [1]. Welding is considered to be an ideal joining technique for thermoplastic composites [2] because it overcomes the difficulties that appear when traditional joining techniques are applied to thermoplastic composites [3]. Welding process in general can be described as joining the parts by fusing their contact surfaces, followed by their cooling (consolidating) under pressure. From the vast amount of available welding techniques, resistance welding has emerged as one of the most promising [4]. It uses an electrically resistive heating element to provide the heat to the bonding interfaces. The heating element remains in the bond after the welding. Resistance welding offers a number of advantages over other welding techniques, like very simple, low cost tooling [5] and little or no surface treatment [6].

Resistance welding of carbon reinforced thermoplastic composites has been extensively investigated in a number of studies. Experimental studies of Hou et al. [7-9] and Ageorges et al. [10,11], although performed mainly on coupon level, give deep insight into the nature of the process and the relation between the process parameters and the quality of the weld. Processing windows for several combinations of materials and heating elements have been established [8,9,11].

Nevertheless, achieving welded joints with consistent quality on larger scale remains the major difficulty concerning resistance welding of carbon reinforced thermoplastic composites. The main cause for this difficulty is current leaking into the laminate, which usually occurs at the edges of the welded specimens as a direct consequence of non-uniform

temperature distribution along the weld [2,10]. Current leaking tends to emerge very early in the process, preventing the welding to be completed, or producing a very weak joint. In this way it also limits the length of the weld.

Very few studies were performed on the possible solutions of the current leaking problem. Inserting a glass reinforced layer [9,10] and inserting a layer of amorphous material by welding semi-crystalline matrix materials (Thermabond® process) [12] have proven successful up until now.

This paper describes an experimental study of resistance welding of carbon fiber thermoplastics performed on large-scale welds. The investigation was mainly focused on preventing the current leaking in the laminates. A novel insulation method of the heating element by coating it with electrically resistive material is introduced and experimentally investigated. The quality of the bond was evaluated by using microscopic scanning and mechanical testing. Additionally, already existing insulation methods for preventing the current leaking are also investigated. The results are compared and discussed. Finally, recommendations for future work are proposed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The material used in this study was continuous carbon fiber reinforced polyetherimide (CF/PEI). The preimpregnated material, supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands, had a 5-harness satin weave configuration and 44,1 %wt resin content. Six-ply laminates, with dimensions of 500x500 mm, were consolidated in the hot platen press, according to the recommendations of the supplier. Welding specimens were subsequently cut in size with a water cooled diamond saw.

Fig. 1. The detail of the experimental welding set-up

A woven stainless steel mesh was used as a material for manufacturing the heating element. The wire diameter was 0.28 mm and the gap 1.54 mm. Three types of heating elements were produced. Type-1 heating element was produced by coating the mesh with soluble polyimide (PI), insulation material that is normally used in the electronic industry for production of circuit boards. It is thermally stable up to over 500°C and chemically resistive. The mesh was degreased and the coating was applied with a brush. The heating element was then cured in an oven in a three step curing cycle up to 300°C. Coating

procedure was repeated three times, when the satisfactory thickness of the coating was achieved. Type-2 heating element was produced by coating the mesh with high temperature resistive paint, normally used in the automotive industry. The paint is electrically resistive and thermally stable up to 600°C. After degreasing the mesh, two layers of the coating were applied by spraying. The heating element was cured in a similar procedure as type-1 heating element. Type-3 heating element is actually a normal, non-treated mesh. It was only degreased prior to impregnating. All three types of heating elements were subsequently impregnated between two resin layers, so that a rich resin content at the bonding surface could be provided. The impregnation process was performed in the hot platen press, using the similar parameters as for consolidating the laminates. The edges of the heating elements were not impregnated, so a clean contact with the clamps was provided. When the heating elements were cut from the impregnated mesh, care was taken that the number of wires in longitudinal direction remained the same, so the resistances of the heating elements would remain constant.

A special experimental set-up was developed for welding large-scale specimens. The lower ceramic support was 1000 mm long, 400 mm wide and partly adjustable in height to provide complete support for different specimen thickness (Fig.1). The loading shaft was made from a silicone rubber block, with pressing area of 50x1000 mm, cased in a U-shaped metal casing to provide a uniform load distribution. The ceramic and rubber materials were carefully chosen to have as similar heat transfer coefficients as possible, so the same temperature profile in the both laminates was obtained. The loading shaft was attached to four pneumatic cylinders that provided controlled loading force.

Fig. 2. Welding overlap configuration

The welded overlap configuration was also adapted to the set-up, as shown in Fig. 2. The lower laminate was used as a support for the clamps, which were one-sided and with the same thickness as the laminates (Fig.1). The clamps were placed close to the upper laminate, providing in that way sufficient contact with the heating element and improving the uniformity of the pressure distribution along the weld. The electric power transformer with maximum DC output of 45 A and 70 V was used to supply the electrical power for the welding experiments.

Resistance welding was performed under constant welding pressure. The input power was varied in the medium range between 60 and 130 KW/m² and the welding time between 35 and 100 seconds. Welded specimens were 200x195 mm, with an overlap of 25 mm, according to ASTM standard. Specimens with two different welding configurations were produced. Specimens welded with type-1 and type-2 heating elements placed between the laminates formed the first group. In this group of welds, electrical insulation was provided by coating (insulating) the mesh itself. The second group was formed by the specimens welded with type-3 heating element, placed between the laminates and an additional insulation layer of PEI or GF/PEI. Electrical insulation in this case was provided by preventing the physical contact between the heating element and carbon fibers from the laminates. There was practically no preparation of the laminates, heating elements and insulation materials prior to welding. Only the PEI film was cleaned with acetone to prevent possible contamination of the weld. To get a better indication of the strength of the weld, compression molded benchmark specimens with resembling geometry were produced. The configuration of the benchmark specimens included also the glass fiber insulation layer.

The quality of the bond was evaluated by mechanical microscopic scanning, lap shear testing and ultrasonic scanning. Lap shear strength tests were performed according to ASTM D 1002. Tested specimens were cut to the standard geometry with a diamond saw from the welded and compression molded specimens and their edges were slightly polished prior to testing. The tests were performed under standard conditions, temperature of 23°C and relative humidity round 50%. The cross-head speed was 1.3 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Current leaking presents the major difficulty in resistance welding of the carbon reinforced thermoplastics today. It occurs when the heating element comes in contact with electrically leading carbon fibers from the laminate. The contact between the heating element and the carbon fibers from the laminate usually occurs at the edges of the welded specimens as a direct consequence of non-uniform temperature distribution along the weld [2,10]. A high temperature gradient present at the edges causes rapid melting or even burning of the matrix

Fig. 3. SEM photo of the weld performed with high temperature coating-enlargement 20x and 50x

in that area and enables the contact between the reinforcing carbon fibers from the laminate and the heating element. In the case of contact, alternative current circuits are formed into the laminate and the laminate itself becomes the heating element. This reduces the current

density in the heating element, preventing in that way uniform and sufficient heating of the welding surface, eventually causing a failed weld in most severe cases. When the heating element is not properly insulated from the laminate, current leaking tends to emerge very early in the process, limiting in that way the length of the weld.

Several methods for preventing the current leaking in large-scale welds were investigated in this study. These methods can be divided into two groups. In the first group, the insulation is provided by a newly introduced coating of the heating element with a certain electrically insulating material and in the second group the insulation is provided by inserting an insulation layer between the laminate and the heating element. Two different insulation materials were tested for each method group, high temperature coating and soluble PI for the first group and a layer of PEI and glass fiber/PEI for the second.

High temperature coating heating elements (type-2) gave satisfactory results. Complete welds were achieved at all combinations of welding parameters, although the coating appeared more sensitive to higher power levels. Two of the welded specimens short-circuited at the end of the welding process at power level of 130 kW/m^2 . The coating adhered well to the resistance wires of the heating element and was uniformly applied along the heating element. The high temperature coating layer was visibly thicker when compared to PI coating. Microscopic scans of the welded overlap, shown in Fig.3, clearly show that the wires were completely and uniformly covered by the coating and the heating element was fully embedded and integrated in the joint. Minor irregularities, like the presence of voids, which are also visible on the photograph in Fig.3, probably had a certain impact on the strength of the weld, but since they were present in each specimen, we were not able to determine it. Some difficulties were also experienced in the impregnation process of the heating element. At higher consolidation pressure in the hot platen press, the coating was pushed of the wires, producing unusable heating elements. At lower consolidation pressure, on the other hand, the coating remained intact, but the resin layers did not adhere properly to the coating. Nevertheless, successful welds were produced with these heating elements.

Fig. 4. SEM photo of the weld performed with GF/PEI insulation-enlargement 20x and 50x

The soluble PI coating heating elements (type-1) gave in general disappointing results. Although it appeared that with several layers of the coating complete insulation of the mesh is provided, all welds failed before completion, even in cases when 8 layers of the coating were applied. Some spots of the heating element remained unprotected at each heating element and caused current leaking into the laminate. This was apparently due to the type of the coating and applying procedure used. Soluble PI coating with low PI content and low viscosity was used for this study, applied with a brush. A more viscous PI solution, sprayed on the mesh would provide better and more uniform coating of the heating element, as it was experienced with the high temperature coating. Nevertheless, it was established that

the PI coating provides electrical insulation and adheres well to the resistance wire without special surface treatment.

The second group of welds performed with type-3 heating element and inserted layer of PEI and GF/PEI as electrical insulation gave also mixed results. Inserting an additional resin layer between the laminates and the heating element did not provide sufficient insulation. Resistance wires from the heating element perforated the PEI film very easy when heated and penetrated into the laminate, getting in contact with the fibers and causing current leaking. Welding was possible to a certain extent only at very low power levels (35-59 KW/m²) and low pressures (under 0.5 MPa). The produced joints were with a very low level of cohesion and lap shear strength, as the tests have proven. Current leaking occurred on almost all specimens before the desired level of bonding was achieved.

An additional glass fiber/PEI layer inserted between the laminates and the heating elements provided complete insulation, as reported in [9,10]. Current leaking did not occur at any of the welded specimens. Microscopic scans of the welded specimens, shown in Fig. 4, revealed a very clean bond with only minor matrix imperfections. The heating element was again completely embedded into the matrix. Glass fiber layer is clearly visible in the scan, as well as the insulation that it provides by preventing the physical contact between the carbon fibers from the laminate and the heating element.

Fig. 5. Mean lap shear strength values of the welded specimens

Mechanical lap shear tests were performed to provide information about the strength of the welds. They were performed according to ASTM D 1002 standard. At least eight welded specimens were tested for each welding configuration. Six coupon specimens were cut from each welded specimen. They yielded rather uniform strength values along the weld, with deviations within 10% of the mean strength. This points to the fact that uniform weld quality was achieved. The summary of the results is presented in Fig. 5. Specimens welded with high temperature coating (type-2) heating element performed the best with respect to the lap shear strength. Their average strength value was 82% of the strength of the reference panels. Considering the facts that these were first tests with this weld configuration and the number of irregularities in the bond that could certainly be improved, it is clear that this type of insulation has a lot of potential. Specimens welded with glass fiber/PEI insulation layer

and type-1 heating element gave also rather satisfactory results. Their main strength value reached 73% of the strength of the compress molded benchmark specimen. This means that they performed slightly worse than the specimens welded with type-1 heating element, despite their better looking weld lay-up in the microscopic scans. This was due to the fact that the glass fiber/PEI insulation layer was not impregnated with the heating element or with the laminate prior to welding. During the welding process, the insulation layer did not have the time to consolidate within the joint properly, producing a weakness in the bond. The specimens welded with PEI film insulation layer were also tested. As expected, they performed below 30% of the benchmark value, proving again that a single PEI ply does not provide sufficient insulation for welding carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics. The specimens welded with soluble PI coating (type-1) heating element were not mechanically tested since no complete weld was achieved.

CONCLUSION

An experimental study on resistance welding of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites has been presented. The investigation was focused on solving the current leaking problem. Since the current leaking problem becomes more severe with enlarging the weld area, the investigation was performed on large-scale welds. Four possible solutions were investigated. The quality of the produced welds was evaluated by mechanical testing and microscopic scanning.

The results revealed that a layer of glass fiber PEI inserted between the welded laminate and the heating element provides complete insulation and produces welds with satisfactory cohesion and strength. The newly introduced high temperature coating of the heating element gave also very promising results. The quality of the weld was comparable with the one made with glass fiber/PEI insulation and the lap shear strength was even higher. Further advantages of the high temperature coating are simpler preparations for the welding process in general and avoiding an additional foreign material in the joint. Other two possible current leaking solutions tested, the soluble PI coating and inserted PEI layer, did not produce satisfactory welds.

The results of the successful insulation methods pointed also to a large improvement potential, especially for the high temperature coating. Therefore, further extensive investigation of this coating method is strongly recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research project was made possible by the support of Ten Cate Advanced Composites through the input of their technical knowledge and material supply.

REFERENCES

1. Don RC, Bastien L, Jakobsen TB, Gillespie Jr. JW. Fusion bonding of thermoplastic composites by resistance heating. SAMPE Journal, 1990;Jan-Feb: 59-66.
2. Eveno EC, Gillespie Jr. JW. Resistance welding of graphite polyetheretherketone composites: an experimental investigation. Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials, 1988;1: 322-38.
3. Beevers A. Welding: the way ahead for thermoplastics? Engineering 1991;231:ACE11-2.
4. Ageorges C, Ye L, Hou M. Advances in fusion bonding techniques for joining thermoplastic matrix composites: a review. Composites Part A, 2001; 32: 839-57.
5. Xiao XR, Hoa SV, Street KN. Repair of thermoplastic resin composites by fusion bonding. Composites Bonding, 1994;ASTM STP 1227: 30-44.

6. Lambing CLT, Don RC, Andersen SM, Holmes ST, Leach BS, Gillespie Jr. JW. Design and manufacture of an automated resistance welder for thermoplastic composites. ANTEC '91: 2527-31
7. Hou M, Friedrich K. Resistance welding of continuous carbon fibre/polypropylene composites. *Plastic, Rubber and Composites Processing and Application*, 1992;18(4): 205-213.
8. Hou M, Ye L, Mai YW. An experimental study of resistance welding of carbon fibre fabric reinforced polyetherimide (CF Fabric/PEI) composite material. *Applied Composite Materials*, 1999;6: 35-49.
9. Hou M, Yang M, Beehag A, Mai YW, Ye L. Resistance welding of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite using alternative heating element. *Composite Structures*, 1999; 47: 667-672.
10. Ageorges C, Ye L, Hou M. Experimental investigation of the resistance welding for thermoplastic-matrix composites. Part I: heating element and heat transfer. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2000; 60: 1027-39.
11. Ageorges C, Ye L, Hou M. Experimental investigation of the resistance welding for thermoplastic-matrix composites. Part II: optimum processing window and mechanical performance. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2000; 60: 1191-1202.
12. Don RC, Gillespie Jr. JW, Lambing CLT. Experimental characterization of processing-performance relationships of resistance welded graphite/polyetheretherketone composite joints. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 1992;32(9): 620-31.